

Abstract Manuscript

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Assessment of an 800 V Electric Vehicle Powertrain: Daily-Cycle Comparison with a 400 V Architecture and Long-term Degradation Projection

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High-voltage (HV) electric vehicle (EV) architectures are increasingly adopted to reduce current levels, improve drivetrain efficiency, and enable high-power charging, while also decreasing electrical losses and conductor requirements compared with conventional 400 V systems. This paper investigates the impact of DC bus voltage on EV powertrain performance using dynamic component models previously verified for accuracy. Two complementary scenarios are examined. First, a controlled comparison between 400 V and 800 V architectures is conducted under identical vehicle and battery configurations using the Worldwide Harmonized Light Vehicles Test Cycle (WLTC), allowing assessment of key electrical and vehicle-level variables, including current demand, state of charge evolution, and energy consumption. Second, the degradation behaviour of a production-representative 800 V EV configuration, parameterized based on the Audi Q6 SUV e-tron quattro (model year 2024–2025), is analysed under repeated drive-cycle operation to evaluate the impact of battery ageing on available capacity and vehicle-level performance. The results provide insight into both the operational advantages and long-term behaviour of high-voltage EV architectures, and establish a practical and realistic framework for their evaluation.

Keywords: Electric Vehicles (EVs), High-Voltage (HV) Architecture, 800 V Systems, Dynamic Simulation, Battery Degradation, WLTC Driving Cycle, Powertrain Modelling

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